

Serbian Society of Soil Science
University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

3rd International and 15th National Congress

SOILS FOR FUTURE UNDER GLOBAL CHALLENGES

21–24 September 2021
Sokobanja, Serbia

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Soils for Future under Global Challenges

PROMOTING THE APPLICATION OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURAL WATER MANAGEMENT IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Abstract

The adoption of smart agricultural water management in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is becoming a priority due to climate change, which increases weather uncertainty, and the necessity to promote a more efficient and sustainable use of resources in agriculture. In this context, a new project - SMARTWATER - is funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Twinning HORIZON 2020 program. The project is coordinated by the University of Banja Luka (BiH) with the aim to promote the application of smart technologies (cloud-based and remote sensing) in the agricultural water management in BiH. The project partners are University of Sarajevo (BiH), Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari (Italy), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain), Instituto Superior de Agronomia (Portugal), and SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL (Italy). The joint research activities started in 2021 at the experimental sites of Aleksandrovac (University of Banja Luka) and Butmir (University of Sarajevo) both characterized by typical continental climate. The objective is to investigate the applicability of smart technologies to improve maize crop productivity under different water and nitrogen treatments. Moreover, the results will indicate the best management practices by means of the most efficient use of resources in the context of water-energy-food nexus and reduction of negative environmental impact.

Keywords: HORIZON 2020, Agricultural Water Management, Smart Technologies, On ground monitoring, Remote Sensing monitoring

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